

ANALYSIS OF DAMPED HARMONIC OSCILLATOR BY MATRIX METHOD

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Abstract: The motion of damped harmonic oscillator capable of oscillating in a medium such as air, water etc. is always opposed by the frictional (or damping) forces which arise from the resistance of the medium or from within the system itself and act opposite to direction of the motion of the body and result in the decrease in the amplitude of the oscillations with time. As a result of the decrease in the amplitude of the oscillations, there is a dissipation of energy of the oscillations and ultimately, the body stops oscillating. The analysis of damped harmonic oscillator is generally done by adopting the classical method. In this paper, we analyze the response (behaviour) of a damped harmonic oscillator by solving its differential equation by the matrix method. The response obtained will provide an expression for the displacement of the damped oscillator from the equilibrium position at any instant. The behaviour of the displacement obtained is determined by the damping factor and the stiffness factor.

Keywords: Behaviour; Displacement; Damped Harmonic Oscillator; Oscillations; Response.

Introduction: In simple harmonic oscillations which persist indefinitely without the loss of amplitude, the energy of the oscillator remains constant throughout the motion. In actual practice, the oscillator is subjected to the frictional (or damping) forces arising from the resistance of the medium or from within the system itself. These dissipative forces reduce the energy of oscillations of the oscillator continuously with time and the amplitude of oscillations gradually decays to zero. Such a mechanism in which the energy of the oscillator reduces due to the frictional (or damping) force arising from the resistance of the medium or from within the system itself and opposing the motion of the oscillator is called damping and the oscillations of such an oscillator are called damped oscillations. The damped oscillations are not simple harmonic in the sense that maximum displacement on either side of the mean position goes on decreasing with time and the motion of the oscillator cannot be termed a periodic because it does not repeat itself exactly, each swing being smaller than that the preceding oscillation. However, when the damping force is small, it does not have any significant effect on the undamped oscillations of the oscillator. In such a case, the frictional (or damping) force arising from the resistance of medium or from within the system itself depends directly only on the velocity of the oscillator. [1-5]

Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors:

If we consider a matrix F of order $n \times n$ with f_{ij} as its elements, then a column matrix T and a constant μ can be found such that

$[F - \mu I]T = 0$, where I is an identity matrix. On solving this equation, we get n homogeneous linear equations which will have a

non-trivial solution if we equate the determinant of their coefficients to zero. When we simplify the determinant equation, we get an n^{th} degree equation in μ , which is known as the characteristic equation of the matrix F and its roots are known as

Eigenvalues. Corresponding to each Eigenvalue, there is a solution in the form of a column matrix which is known as Eigenvector. [6, 7]

Formulation:

To derive the differential equation of damped harmonic oscillator:

Considering a damped mechanical oscillator in the form of a body attached to one end of a spring of stiffness constant K the other end of which is fixed to a rigid support. If the body is oscillating in a medium like air, water etc. and it is at the displaced position $\psi(t)$ from the equilibrium position at any instant t , then the body is subjected to the following forces:

- i) Damping force (F_d). It arises from the resistance of medium or from within the system itself and depends directly upon

the velocity of the body i.e. $F_d = -r \dot{\psi}(t)$, where r is damping constant and the negative sign indicates that the

motion of the body is opposed by the damping force. $\dot{\psi} \equiv \frac{d\psi}{dt}$.

- ii) Restoring force (F_s). It depends directly upon the displacement of the oscillator from mean position i.e. $F_s = -K \psi(t)$,

where K is stiffness constant and is also known as force constant, and the negative sign indicates that the motion of

the body is opposed by the restoring force. [2-4]

The application of Newton's second law of motion provides

$$m\ddot{\psi}(t) = F_d + F_s, \text{ where } m \text{ is the mass of the body and } \ddot{\psi}(t) \text{ is its linear acceleration.}$$

$$\text{Or } m\ddot{\psi}(t) = -r \dot{\psi}(t) - K \psi(t)$$

$$\text{Or } \ddot{\psi}(t) = -\frac{r}{m} \dot{\psi}(t) - \frac{K}{m} \psi(t)$$

Or
$$\ddot{y}(t) + \frac{r}{m} \dot{y}(t) + \frac{K}{m} y(t) = 0 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

In equation (1), which is known as a differential equation of damped harmonic oscillator, $\frac{r}{m}$ represents the damping term and $\frac{K}{m}$ represents the stiffness term.

To solve the differential equation of damped harmonic oscillator:

To solve equation (1) i.e. to obtain the response (displacement) of the damped harmonic oscillator, we first write the initial boundary conditions as follows:

- (i) If the maximum value of displacement of the body from the equilibrium position is assumed to be y_0 and we measure the time from the instant when the body is at the position of its maximum displacement from the equilibrium position, then at $t = 0, y(0) = y_0$.
- (ii) Since at the instant $t = 0, y(0) = y_0$, which is maximum, therefore, the velocity $\dot{y}(0) = 0$ as the body is at rest at the instant $t = 0$.

Further, let us substitute $y(t) = y_1(t) \dots\dots\dots (2)$

And $\dot{y}_1(t) = y_2(t) \dots\dots\dots (3)$

We can rewrite equation (1) as

$$\dot{y}_2(t) + \frac{r}{m} y_2(t) + \frac{K}{m} y_1(t) = 0$$

Or $\dot{y}_2(t) = -\frac{K}{m} y_1(t) - \frac{r}{m} y_2(t) \dots\dots (4)$

We can write the equations (3) and (4) in the matrix form as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{y}_1(t) \\ \dot{y}_2(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -\frac{K}{m} & -\frac{r}{m} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_1(t) \\ y_2(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

On equating the determinant of $\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -\frac{K}{m} & -\frac{r}{m} \end{bmatrix}$ to zero, we can obtain its characteristic equation as

$$\begin{vmatrix} 0 - \mu & 1 \\ -\frac{K}{m} & -\frac{r}{m} - \mu \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

On expanding the determinant, we get

$$\mu^2 + \frac{r}{m} \mu + \frac{K}{m} = 0 \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

This equation (5) is quadratic in μ and its roots are given by

$$\mu = \frac{-\frac{r}{m} \pm \sqrt{(\frac{r}{m})^2 - \frac{4K}{m}}}{2}$$

Or $\mu = -\frac{r}{2m} \pm \sqrt{(\frac{r}{2m})^2 - \frac{K}{m}}$

Therefore, the roots of the equation (5) are $\mu_1 = -\frac{r}{2m} + \sqrt{(\frac{r}{2m})^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \dots\dots\dots (6)$

And $\mu_2 = -\frac{r}{2m} - \sqrt{(\frac{r}{2m})^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \dots\dots\dots (7)$

The product of roots is given by

$$\mu_1 \mu_2 = \left(-\frac{r}{2m} + \sqrt{(\frac{r}{2m})^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) \left(-\frac{r}{2m} - \sqrt{(\frac{r}{2m})^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right)$$

On simplifying the right hand side of this equation, we get

$$\mu_1 \mu_2 = \frac{K}{m} \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

Also, the sum of roots is given by

$$\mu_1 + \mu_2 = \left(-\frac{r}{2m} + \sqrt{(\frac{r}{2m})^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) + \left(-\frac{r}{2m} - \sqrt{(\frac{r}{2m})^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right)$$

Or $\mu_1 + \mu_2 = -\frac{r}{m} \dots\dots\dots (9)$

To determine Eigenvectors:

The Eigenvector corresponding to the root $\mu = \mu_1 = -\frac{r}{2m} + \sqrt{(\frac{r}{2m})^2 - \frac{K}{m}}$ is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 - \mu_1 & 1 \\ -\frac{K}{m} & -\frac{r}{m} - \mu_1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} t_1 \\ t_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

This results

$$-\mu_1 t_1 + t_2 = 0 \dots\dots\dots (10)$$

And

$$-\frac{K}{m} t_1 - \left(\frac{r}{m} + \mu_1\right) t_2 = 0 \dots\dots\dots (11)$$

Solving equations (10) and (11), we can write

$$\begin{bmatrix} t_1 \\ t_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \\ \mu_1 - \frac{K}{m} \end{bmatrix}$$

And the Eigenvector for the root $\mu = \mu_2 = -\frac{r}{2m} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}$ is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 - \mu_2 & 1 \\ -\frac{K}{m} & -\frac{r}{m} - \mu_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} t_1 \\ t_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

This results

$$-\mu_2 t_1 + t_2 = 0 \dots\dots\dots (12)$$

And

$$-\frac{K}{m} t_1 - \left(\frac{r}{m} + \mu_2\right) t_2 = 0 \dots\dots\dots (13)$$

Solving equations (12) and (13), we can write

$$\begin{bmatrix} t_1 \\ t_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \\ \mu_2 - \frac{K}{m} \end{bmatrix}$$

The matrix of Eigenvectors is $\begin{bmatrix} \mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1 & \mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \\ \mu_1 - \frac{K}{m} & \mu_2 - \frac{K}{m} \end{bmatrix}$.

Let $P = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1 & \mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \\ \mu_1 - \frac{K}{m} & \mu_2 - \frac{K}{m} \end{bmatrix}$, then the determinant of P i.e. |P| is given by

$$|P| = \begin{vmatrix} \mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1 & \mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \\ \mu_1 - \frac{K}{m} & \mu_2 - \frac{K}{m} \end{vmatrix}$$

On expanding the determinant and making use of equation (9), we get

$$|P| = (\mu_2 - \mu_1) \left(\frac{K}{m} + \frac{r}{m} + 1\right)$$

The inverse of P which is also a matrix is given by

$$P^{-1} = \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1) \left(\frac{K}{m} + \frac{r}{m} + 1\right)} \begin{bmatrix} \mu_2 - \frac{K}{m} & -(\mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1) \\ -(\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m}) & \mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

To Determine $Pe^{\mu t}P^{-1}$:

$$Pe^{\mu t}P^{-1} =$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1 & \mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \\ \mu_1 - \frac{K}{m} & \mu_2 - \frac{K}{m} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \exp(\mu_1 t) & 0 \\ 0 & \exp(\mu_2 t) \end{bmatrix} \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1) \left(\frac{K}{m} + \frac{r}{m} + 1\right)} \begin{bmatrix} \mu_2 - \frac{K}{m} & -(\mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1) \\ -(\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m}) & \mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1) \left(\frac{K}{m} + \frac{r}{m} + 1\right)} \times \begin{bmatrix} (\mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1) \exp(\mu_1 t) & (\mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1) \exp(\mu_2 t) \\ (\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m}) \exp(\mu_1 t) & (\mu_2 - \frac{K}{m}) \exp(\mu_2 t) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mu_2 - \frac{K}{m} & -(\mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1) \\ -(\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m}) & \mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1) \left(\frac{K}{m} + \frac{r}{m} + 1\right)} \times \begin{bmatrix} (\mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1)(\mu_2 - \frac{K}{m}) \exp(\mu_1 t) - & (\mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1) (\mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1) [\exp(\mu_2 t) - \exp(\mu_1 t)] \\ (\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m})(\mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1) \exp(\mu_2 t) & -(\mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1)(\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m}) \exp(\mu_1 t) + \\ (\mu_2 - \frac{K}{m})(\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m}) [\exp(\mu_1 t) - \exp(\mu_2 t)] & (\mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1)(\mu_2 - \frac{K}{m}) \exp(\mu_2 t) \end{bmatrix}$$

Now applying the initial boundary conditions: $\psi_1(0) = \psi(0) = \psi_0$ and $\psi_2(0) = \dot{\psi}(0) = 0$ provides

$$\begin{bmatrix} \psi_1(t) \\ \psi_2(t) \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1) \left(\frac{K}{m} + \frac{r}{m} + 1\right)} \times$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} (\mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1)(\mu_2 - \frac{K}{m}) \exp(\mu_1 t) - (\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m})(\mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1) \exp(\mu_2 t) & (\mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1)(\mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1) [\exp(\mu_2 t) - \exp(\mu_1 t)] \\ (\mu_2 - \frac{K}{m})(\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m}) [\exp(\mu_1 t) - \exp(\mu_2 t)] & -(\mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1)(\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m}) \exp(\mu_1 t) + (\mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1)(\mu_2 - \frac{K}{m}) \exp(\mu_2 t) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \psi_0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Or

$$\begin{bmatrix} \psi_1(t) \\ \psi_2(t) \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1) \left(\frac{K}{m} + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \right)} \begin{bmatrix} \psi_0 [(\mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1)(\mu_2 - \frac{K}{m}) \exp(\mu_1 t) - (\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m})(\mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1) \exp(\mu_2 t)] \\ \psi_0 (\mu_2 - \frac{K}{m})(\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m}) [\exp(\mu_1 t) - \exp(\mu_2 t)] \end{bmatrix}$$

This results

$$\psi_1(t) = \frac{\psi_0 [(\mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1)(\mu_2 - \frac{K}{m}) \exp(\mu_1 t) - (\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m})(\mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1) \exp(\mu_2 t)]}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1) \left(\frac{K}{m} + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \right)}$$

Or $\psi(t) = \frac{\psi_0 [(\mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1)(\mu_2 - \frac{K}{m}) \exp(\mu_1 t) - (\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m})(\mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1) \exp(\mu_2 t)]}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1) \left(\frac{K}{m} + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \right)} \dots\dots\dots (14)$

And

$$\psi_2(t) = \frac{\psi_0 (\mu_2 - \frac{K}{m})(\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m}) [\exp(\mu_1 t) - \exp(\mu_2 t)]}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1) \left(\frac{K}{m} + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \right)}$$

Or $\psi(t) = \frac{\psi_0 (\mu_2 - \frac{K}{m})(\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m}) [\exp(\mu_1 t) - \exp(\mu_2 t)]}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1) \left(\frac{K}{m} + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \right)} \dots\dots\dots (15)$

Now making use of equations (8) and (9), we can find that

$$(\mu_1 + \frac{r}{m} + 1)(\mu_2 - \frac{K}{m}) = \mu_2 \left(\frac{K}{m} + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \right) \dots\dots\dots (16)$$

$$\text{And } (\mu_1 - \frac{K}{m})(\mu_2 + \frac{r}{m} + 1) = \mu_1 \left(\frac{K}{m} + \frac{r}{m} + 1 \right) \dots\dots\dots (17)$$

Put equations (16) and (17) in equation (14), we obtain

$$\psi(t) = \frac{\psi_0 [\mu_2 \exp(\mu_1 t) - \mu_1 \exp(\mu_2 t)]}{\mu_2 - \mu_1}$$

Or $\psi(t) = \frac{\psi_0 [\mu_1 \exp(\mu_2 t) - \mu_2 \exp(\mu_1 t)]}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} \dots\dots\dots (18)$

Substituting equations (7) and (8) in equation (18), we get

$$\psi(t) = \frac{\psi_0 \left\{ \left(-\frac{r}{2m} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) \exp \left[\left(-\frac{r}{2m} - \sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) t \right] - \left(-\frac{r}{2m} - \sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) \exp \left[\left(-\frac{r}{2m} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) t \right] \right\}}{2 \sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}}$$

Or

$$\psi(t) = \frac{\psi_0 \exp\left(-\frac{r}{2m}t\right) \left\{ \left(\frac{r}{2m}\right) \left[\exp \left[\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) t \right] - \exp \left[-\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) t \right] \right] + \left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) \left[\exp \left[\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) t \right] + \exp \left[-\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) t \right] \right] \right\}}{2 \sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}}$$

Or

$$\psi(t) = \psi_0 \exp\left(-\frac{r}{2m}t\right) \left\{ \frac{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right) \exp \left[\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) t \right] - \exp \left[-\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) t \right]}{2} + \frac{\exp \left[\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) t \right] + \exp \left[-\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}} \right) t \right]}{2} \right\} \dots\dots\dots (19)$$

This equation (19) provides an expression for the displacement of the damped harmonic oscillator and reveals that the nature of its displacement depends on the nature of the quantity $\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}$ which may be real, zero or imaginary depending upon the values of $\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2$ and $\frac{K}{m}$. We have the following three cases:

Case I: If the values of $\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2$ and $\frac{K}{m}$ are so chosen that $\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 > \frac{K}{m}$, then the quantity $\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}$ is real. In such a case, equation (19) can be rewritten as

$$\psi(t) = \psi_0 \exp\left(-\frac{r}{2m}t\right) \left[\frac{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}} \sinh\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}t\right) + \cosh\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}t\right) \right] \dots\dots\dots (20)$$

It is clear from the equation (20) that the behaviour of oscillator is non – oscillatory or aperiodic as the right hand side of the equation contains the terms $\sinh\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}t\right)$ and $\cosh\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}t\right)$ which are non-periodic functions of time, and the amplitude of oscillations of the oscillator decreases with time without changing sign. It means that if the oscillator is displaced once from its mean position it returns to the mean position quite slowly without oscillating. The behaviour of the oscillator in such a case is said to be over damped or dead beat. Thus for the oscillations to be dead beat or over damped, damping term $\frac{r}{2m}$ is as large as possible and for this damping coefficient r is large.

Case II: If the values of $\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2$ and $\frac{K}{m}$ are so chosen that $\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 = \frac{K}{m}$, then the quantity $\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}$ is zero. In this case, equation (19) reveals that the displacement of the damped harmonic oscillator is indeterminate, which is not possible. If the quantity $\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}$ is so small that it approaches zero, then on expanding the exponential terms containing the quantity $\sqrt{R^2 - \frac{4k}{c}}$ and keeping only the first two terms, we can rewrite equation (19) as

$$\psi(t) = \psi_0 \exp\left(-\frac{r}{2m}t\right) \left\{ \frac{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}} \frac{1 + \left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}t\right) - [1 - \left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}t\right)]}{2} + \frac{1 + \left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}t\right) + [1 - \left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}t\right)]}{2} \right\}$$

Or

$$\psi(t) = \psi_0 \left(1 + \frac{r}{2m}t\right) \exp\left(-\frac{r}{2m}t\right) \dots\dots\dots (21)$$

It is clear from the equation (21) that the behaviour of the oscillator is non – oscillatory, and the amplitude of oscillations of the oscillator decays to zero in the minimum possible time. The behaviour of the damped oscillator in such a case is neither over damped nor dead beat, it is said to be critically damped.

Case III: If the values of $\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2$ and $\frac{K}{m}$ are so chosen that $\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 < \frac{K}{m}$, then the quantity $\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}$ is imaginary. We can rewrite the quantity $\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}}$ as

$$\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 - \frac{K}{m}} = i \sqrt{\frac{K}{m} - \left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2} \dots\dots\dots (22)$$

Using equation (22), we can rewrite equation (19) as

$$\psi(t) = \psi_0 \exp\left(-\frac{r}{2m}t\right) \left[\frac{\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)}{\sqrt{\frac{K}{m} - \left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2}} \sin\left(\sqrt{\frac{K}{m} - \left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2}t\right) + \cos\left(\sqrt{\frac{K}{m} - \left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2}t\right) \right] \dots\dots\dots (23)$$

To simplify equation (23) further, let $\frac{\psi_0 \left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)}{\sqrt{\frac{K}{m} - \left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2}} = \mathcal{A} \cos \varphi \dots\dots (24)$

And $\psi_0 = \mathcal{A} \sin \varphi \dots\dots (25)$

Squaring and adding equations (24) and (25), we obtain

$$\mathcal{A} = \frac{\psi_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{r^2}{4mK}}} \dots\dots (26)$$

Dividing equations (25) and (24), we obtain

$$\varphi = \tan^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{4mK}{r^2} - 1} \dots\dots (27)$$

Then equation (23) becomes

$$\psi(t) = \mathcal{A} \exp\left(-\frac{r}{2m}t\right) \left[\sin\left(\sqrt{\frac{K}{m} - \left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2}t\right) + \varphi \right] \dots\dots\dots (28)$$

It is clear from the equation (28) that the behaviour of the oscillator is oscillatory with amplitude $\mathcal{A} \exp\left(-\frac{r}{2m}t\right)$ which is decreasing exponentially with time, and the oscillating frequency of the oscillator is $\frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{K}{m} - \left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2}$. The behaviour of the damped oscillator in such a case is said to be lightly damped as the oscillator takes a long time to return to its equilibrium position.

Conclusions: In this paper, we have obtained the response (i.e. displacement) of the damped harmonic oscillator by matrix method. We concluded that the behaviour of the damped harmonic oscillator can be made oscillatory or non-oscillatory depending on the values of stiffness factor $\frac{K}{m}$ and damping factor $\frac{r}{2m}$. In case $\left(\frac{r}{2m}\right)^2 < \frac{K}{m}$, the behaviour of the oscillator is

oscillatory and in such a case there is an exponential decrease in the amplitude of oscillations of the oscillator with time and the motion of the oscillator ceases after a long time and the oscillator is said to be a lightly damped. In case $(\frac{r}{2m})^2 > \frac{K}{m}$, the behaviour of the oscillator is non – oscillatory or aperiodic and in such a case the amplitude of oscillations of the oscillator decreases with time without changing sign and the oscillator is said to be over damped or dead beat.. It can be inferred from the discussion that the energy of oscillator which depends directly upon the square of amplitude, therefore, decreases with time due to an exponential decrease of amplitude in a lightly damped harmonic oscillator.

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